

Insights and perceptions about bodybuilding from competitive bodybuilders: A thematic analysis of YouTube videos

Andrew Mahmood¹& Alyssa Munton²

¹University College Dublin (Ireland)

²University of Saskatchewan (Canada)

andrewmahmood8@gmail.com

Copyright. 2017–2024. Psychreg Journal of Psychology
An open access initiative by Psychreg Ltd
ISSN: 2515-138X

Bodybuilding is a significant area of study in psychology, as body image and self-perceptions are essential to understanding human behaviour and mental processes. This study investigated personal experiences with bodybuilding as shared in YouTube videos. Specifically, the research aimed to explore the insights and perceptions of competitive bodybuilders regarding their practices. Transcripts of five YouTube videos were analysed using thematic analysis, resulting in five key themes: (1) Influenced by social factors, (2) Bodybuilding as a coping mechanism, (3) Taking it to the extreme, (4) High prevalence of steroid use, and (5) Body dissatisfaction. The theme *Taking it to the extreme* was further divided into two subthemes: *Obsession* and *Do whatever it takes*. A narrative linking these themes also emerged from the analysis. The findings revealed that bodybuilding is associated with self-comparisons to idealised body types, exercise addiction, eating disorders, muscle dysmorphia, and steroid use. Future research should explore other social media platforms to examine whether the insights and perceptions of bodybuilders differ from those shared on YouTube.

Keywords: bodybuilding; body image; body dissatisfaction; health psychology; self-esteem

In North America, people take drastic measures to look a certain way; this is particularly true in the sport of bodybuilding (Klein, 1986). Bodybuilding is an important topic of study in psychology, as body image and self-perceptions are crucial to understanding the human mind and behaviour. There are a variety of factors related to bodybuilding, such as why people begin, what it entails, and what it does to the body. The purpose of this study is to explore the insights and perceptions of competitive bodybuilders in regard to bodybuilding using YouTube as a data source.

Bodybuilding is a relevant field of discussion in psychology because it has many implications for the body as well as the mind. There are numerous benefits associated with bodybuilding. A literature review by O'Connor et al. (2010) examined a wide array of research on bodybuilding. The researchers found that bodybuilding reduces anxiety in healthy adults, reduces the intensity of pain in patients with osteoarthritis and fibromyalgia, improves cognition in older adults, improves sleep, reduces fatigue and depressive symptoms, and improves self-esteem. Similar results were found in a study conducted by Dimeo and colleagues (2001), who found that weight training resulted in a clinically significant reduction in depression among participants. An additional study by Tsutsumi and colleagues (1997) found that strength training resulted in significant improvements in physical fitness, self-efficacy, and overall mood in a sample of participants.

It is also important to study bodybuilding because of the potential negatives that may be associated with it. A study by Blouin and Goldfield (1995) found that bodybuilders reported greater body dissatisfaction and lower self-esteem than either sampled runners or martial artists. This low self-esteem common in bodybuilders can sometimes manifest itself as a specific form of body dysmorphia known as muscle dysmorphia, or bigorexia. Bodybuilders with muscle dysmorphia obsess about being as muscular or as lean as possible, even when they are already in what most people would consider good shape. They may spend countless hours in the gym, excessive money on supplements, or engage in deviant eating patterns (Leone et al., 2005). Research also shows that anabolic steroids are often used in competitive bodybuilding in order to enhance strength and physique (Yesalis & Bahrke, 2002). This is a concern as long-term use of anabolic steroids may lead to complications, such as higher risk of heart attack, aggressive behaviour, liver cancer, and even death (Daly et al., 2003). Conducting further research on the negative consequences associated with bodybuilding could bring increased awareness and potentially discourage unsafe practices for people who may be considering starting a weight training regimen.

In addition, studying bodybuilding using YouTube as a data source represents a unique and important research opportunity. There are many reasons why YouTube is an important source of data. Within the field of psychology, there is little to no research on what YouTube videos have to say about bodybuilding. Today, YouTube is one of the top visited websites across the world, with over 2.5 billion monthly viewers (Walsh, 2024). Despite the popularity of the video sharing site, there has been a lack of social science research directed toward its content, especially when compared to other social network websites (Thelwall et al., 2011). Analysing information presented on YouTube can lead to a better understanding of what information people are getting about bodybuilding. This is due to the fact that many people use YouTube as a source of knowledge and entertainment. Additionally, much of the previous research on bodybuilding comes from quantitative studies, as well as studies in sports journals.

This highlights the need for a qualitative study on the subject. A key advantage of qualitative research is its flexibility in considering a wide range of materials as data (Henwood & Pidgeon, 1992). This makes it particularly well-suited to research utilising YouTube as a non-traditional data source, which may not align easily with the constraints of quantitative methods. Another significant strength of qualitative research is its focus on representing reality through the perspectives of participants (Henwood & Pidgeon, 1992) – or, in this case, the creators of YouTube videos. This approach enables participants or data to construct meaning from their experiences, incorporating the surrounding context. By contrast, quantitative studies often remove or control for context (Henwood & Pidgeon, 1992), potentially overlooking key aspects of the human experience. YouTube videos inherently reflect the context in which they were created, making a qualitative approach well-suited to capturing this nuance.

When looking at social media as a data source, one must consider the influence that social media has on individuals. Viewing and interacting with social media can influence our self-image and, more specifically, our body-image. Self-image can be defined as the way one thinks and feels about themselves that influences their self-esteem, body esteem, and body satisfaction (Barlett et al., 2005). Similarly, body image can be defined as the thoughts, feelings, and behaviour towards one's own body shape, appearance, and attractiveness (Cash, 2004). Essentially, body image is one component of our self-image. Another related concept is body dissatisfaction, which refers to negative thoughts and feelings that an individual holds about their body and physical appearance (Cash, 1990).

Past literature has found a direct link between social media use and body dissatisfaction (Fardouly & Vartanian, 2016). This is a well-known phenomenon that likely occurs due to the exposure to unrealistic images that plague social media. These unrealistic images come in the form of celebrity or influencer posts and content that is edited or enhanced. When viewing social media content, individuals often compare themselves to what they see on screen, and inevitably cannot emulate these unrealistic body standards (Fardouly & Vartanian, 2016). People often internalize what they see online and turn it into goals for themselves. For example, studies have shown that after viewing social media content, people have a greater drive for thinness (females) or muscularity (males), higher body dissatisfaction, and increased body surveillance (Fardouly & Vartanian, 2016). These constant comparisons based on appearance can lead to negative body image (Fardouly & Vartanian, 2016).

When looking specifically at men, there are fewer studies examining the effect of media on their self-image when compared to studies looking at women. A meta-analysis by Barlett et al. (2008) found that mass media had a significant effect on men, showing that they felt worse about their own bodies after exposure (Barlett et al., 2008). Additionally, the meta-analysis found that mass media pressures led to body dissatisfaction, poorer body-esteem, self-esteem, psychological disorders such as depression, and behaviours such as excessive exercising (Barlett et al., 2008). This meta-analysis looked at mass media as a whole, rather than focussing specifically on social media. Therefore, it is important to gain a better understanding of how social media specifically impacts men's body-image. Furthermore, most studies addressing the impact of social media on body image looked at more traditional forms of social media such as Facebook and Instagram. More studies are needed to assess the impact of newer and alternative forms of social media, such as YouTube, Snapchat, and Tik-Tok.

As demonstrated above, there is some conflicting research regarding the subject of bodybuilding within the field of psychology. Some studies found mental health benefits, and others claim it can be detrimental to mental health. The purpose of this study is to explore the topic of bodybuilding using YouTube as a data source. A data driven approach will be adopted to determine which end of the spectrum competitive bodybuilders lean. Transcripts of the selected videos will be produced and analysed using Braun and Clarke's method of thematic analysis (2006). Specifically, our research question is, what are the insights and perceptions of competitive bodybuilders in regard to bodybuilding?

METHODS

Data Sources

The data sources included five videos from YouTube, all of which discussed several aspects of bodybuilding and body image. The first video was "Inside Westside Barbell, Powerlifting's Most Exclusive and Controversial Gym" by VICE Sports (2018). This video was a short documentary, including interviews with the owner of the gym as well as several gym members. The second video was "Jay Cutler Interview: I Didn't Want To Be Big, I Wanted To Win | Iron Cinema" by Generation Iron Fitness & Bodybuilding Network (2017). As indicated by the title, this video was an interview with Jay Cutler, a four-time Mr. Olympia champion bodybuilder. The third video was "THE SECRET TO GETTING BIG - Rich Piana" by Rich Piana (2015). This was a self-recorded video giving advice as to how to gain muscle, according to the late bodybuilder Rich Piana. The fourth video included in our

analysis was “Confessions Of A 'Natural' Bodybuilder | Pete Hartwig | 2018” by Pete Hartwig (2018). This video was a short documentary exploring bodybuilding culture from the eyes of Pete Hartwig, a world champion “natural” bodybuilder. The final video was “The Truth About Natural Bodybuilding...” by Nick’s Strength and Power (2017). This video is a self-recorded video of Nick Miller, a competitive bodybuilder, sharing his experience with ‘natural’ bodybuilding.

Data collection

Using YouTube, a simple search for “bodybuilding” was conducted. Specifically, the search was conducted while signed out of all YouTube accounts and using private browsing to minimize bias in the suggested results. The first 50 YouTube results were used as a data set due to their relevance, engagement, and quality (“YouTube Search – How YouTube Works,” n.d.). As an initial screening process, all 50 videos were viewed at two times speed to assess for relevance to the research topic. Videos focused on motivational talks, exercise routines, and dietary advice demonstrated a lack of content regarding insights or perceptions; therefore, these were excluded from analysis. Additionally, videos that lacked sufficient dialogue were excluded due to not being conducive to coding. The remaining videos consisted of individuals sharing personal accounts or providing advice. This style of video was well suited to thematic analysis and best facilitated our research question due to being rich in dialogue and expressing personal thoughts and feelings. Videos of this style posted by the same YouTube channel, or different videos featuring the same individual were excluded to ensure variety in the data. Finally, any videos that came from recreational as opposed to competitive bodybuilders were also excluded because this study aimed to focus only on those who compete. In total, five videos remained after applying the exclusionary criteria. These included content from both world-record bodybuilders and lesser-known individuals, as well as from self-identified ‘natural’ bodybuilders and others who used steroids.

Data analysis

Thematic analysis as described by Braun and Clarke (2006) was applied to the chosen videos. This process consists of six phases undertaken sequentially, resulting in the generation of themes from a qualitative data set. Specifically, an inductive approach was conducted to allow for the data itself to facilitate the generation of themes. This was chosen based on a recommendation from Braun and Clarke (2006) suggesting that inductive analysis should be used when new territory or novel insights are sought in the study. This was chosen as opposed to a deductive approach, which the authors felt would constrain the generation of potential themes due to data only being analysed within pre-existing theoretical frameworks. Furthermore, according to ATLAS.ti, due to deductive analysis relying on pre-determined themes, it can limit the finding of novel or unexpected codes and themes in the data.

Phase 1

The first step in thematic analysis is to familiarise oneself with the data (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Initially, all five of the YouTube videos were viewed by both authors together. The videos were then divided among the authors to save time during the transcription process. One author was given the two longest videos, and the other the three shortest videos. Each assigned video was re-watched, and verbatim transcripts were generated. All five transcripts were then read by both authors together. While reading, the authors underlined quotations that pertained directly to the research question.

Phase 2

The second step in thematic analysis is to generate codes from the data. A code refers to a word or phrase that represents the researcher’s interpretation of patterns of meaning within the data set (Braun & Clarke, 2006). The underlying quotations from phase one were analysed by both authors, and preliminary codes were generated. These were written on sticky notes to allow for visualization and physical manipulation of the data. These codes were discussed among the authors, leading to the generation of new codes, modifying of preexisting codes, or the discarding of codes that were deemed

unnecessary or not relevant to the research question. Eventually, a final set of codes were created and were organised into separate categories for subsequent generation of themes.

Phase 3

The third step in thematic analysis involves the generation of themes from the codes generated in the previous step (Braun & Clarke, 2006). The final set of codes were analysed by both authors, and patterns and commonalities between them were discussed. Codes that explored similar ideas were combined and were placed into piles representing potential candidate themes. At this stage, any code that was deemed to be unrelated or could not be fit into a candidate theme was discarded. Disagreements in relation to codes and themes were dealt with on an individual basis. Following discussion, several candidate themes were generated for subsequent analysis.

Phase 4

The fourth step in thematic analysis involves refining and reviewing the themes from the previous step to generate final themes (Braun & Clarke, 2006). All the codes were analysed to ensure that they fit within the framework of the proposed theme. This allowed for a candidate thematic map to be generated, as seen in Figure 1. At this point there were five candidate themes that emerged, and there appeared to be a distinction among them which resulted in the themes being assigned to the category “Before starting bodybuilding” or “After starting bodybuilding”.

Figure 1
Candidate thematic map

Phase 5

The fifth step of thematic analysis is to define and name the themes generated (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Once the candidate thematic map was generated, each theme was analysed individually from the others. If any of the themes were too broad, subthemes were generated to more accurately represent the coded data. This occurred in our third theme, Taking it to the extreme. The codes seemed to describe two separate ideas, which is why this theme was subdivided into Obsession and Do whatever it takes. Additionally, at this stage the distinction between “Before starting bodybuilding” and “After starting bodybuilding” was eliminated because it did not alter the overall results. In total, five themes were generated, with one theme being subdivided into two sub-themes.

Phase 6

The sixth and final step of thematic analysis is writing up the analysis of the generated themes (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Specific passages from the videos were provided to support the themes and to provide discussion.

RESULTS

Following analysis of the codes, five themes emerged. A visual representation of the themes is reflected in Figure 2 and is described in the following text.

Figure 2
Thematic map of YouTube videos about body building

Theme 1: Influenced by social factors

A common theme throughout the videos was the notion that someone or something inspired these men to start bodybuilding. These social influences included famous bodybuilders, superheroes, and parents. Two of the videos specifically discussed superheroes in comics. As children, the bodybuilders were exposed to muscular fictional characters and looked up to them as the ideal body type, which influenced them to start bodybuilding. For example, in his interview, Jay Cutler says “I was a huge fan of the cartoon characters, whether it be Spiderman or Superman or these kinds of characters and I remember picking up a magazine when I was 12 and I saw Chris Dickerson for Mr. Olympia. I thought wow I want to look like that because that kind of rivalled what I thought is like superhero type physiques.” In this video Jay is expressing how these characters influenced his decision to start bodybuilding. Pete Hartwig also mentions that his desire to start bodybuilding was influenced by media portrayals of superheroes. Specifically, Pete says: “Since I was 10 years old I always wanted to look like a superhero, like Arnold Schwarzenegger.” This passage once again demonstrates the idolization of superheroes and the real men who resemble them. Motivation to start bodybuilding may also come from one’s personal connections. Many of the men who work out at Westside Barbell were influenced by Louie Simmons to start bodybuilding. For example, Jason Coker discusses how he wanted to be taught by “the best fucking teacher...knows all sorts of shit.” He continues and says, “a

lot of times you're lifting for the old man, lifting for him is a driving force." Similarly, Nick was influenced by his father to start bodybuilding. In the video, Nick says "My dad was a bodybuilder, so you know he was able to show me all his bodybuilding pictures." Nick looked up to his father and wanted to be a bodybuilder like his role model. All of these examples demonstrate how social influences can play a large role in one's decision to start bodybuilding.

Theme 2: Bodybuilding as a coping mechanism

Many of the men expressed that prior to starting bodybuilding they experienced depression, anxiety, getting into legal trouble, or low self-esteem. This led many of them to turn to bodybuilding to cope with and improve their situations. Pete Hartwig discusses that because he struggled with mental illness and insecurity, he started training. He says: "I've struggled a lot in my life with depression and anxiety and it's not something that I talk about a lot." He also says: "as a young kid, I was very lonely and isolated and I felt that you know, if I got big arms and good abs and just had this really amazing body that it would make me happy." These quotations illustrate that Pete wanted something in his life that he could turn to in order to cope with his insecurity and isolation. He decided that improving his physique would make him feel better, therefore he started bodybuilding as a coping mechanism. Louie Simmons expresses a similar idea; he also struggled with low self-esteem and needed something to help him cope with that. In an interview, Louie mentions that he had "low self-esteem probably, I didn't have much growing up and so I got in a lot of fights, but weights turned me around, it gave me self-confidence." Bodybuilding was used as a coping mechanism and allowed him to become confident in himself. Other members of the Westside Barbell gym expressed similar needs for a positive outlet for their negative situations. For example, when asked why he got into bodybuilding, Anthony Olivera says he did it to "keep myself out of trouble...I was addicted to opiates." Similarly, Jason Coker used bodybuilding as a way to improve his time in prison. He explains that he "started power lifting in prison" which was used to make the best of a bad situation. Jay Cutler discusses how bodybuilding was a way to "escape his reality", allowing for him to focus on getting stronger and ignore all the negatives in his life. These quotations demonstrate how bodybuilding was used as a coping mechanism to improve and cope with their life and feelings.

Theme 3: Taking it to the extreme

Obsession

Throughout the YouTube videos almost all of the men discuss the extreme lengths they have taken as a part of their training and lifestyle as a bodybuilder. For many of them, the gym has become the most important thing in their lives. For example, Pete talks about how "ever since I was really young, I've been completely obsessed with the human body...I'd go out into the yard and do chin ups, really try and build up my physique, I'd do push-ups, I even tried to sleep in a crunch position once." He continues saying that "when I was 14 years old I started weights training and then did weights training through high school; went to uni, studied the human body, try and learn about training, nutrition." Essentially, since he was a kid Pete has dedicated himself to bodybuilding, and it has become a central aspect in his life. Many of the other bodybuilders share a similar extreme lifestyle, revolving around bodybuilding. For example, Jay Cutler says "I knew I wanted to dedicate my life to it." For him this meant doing everything he could to get to the gym and workout, specifically he says "I would put \$2.00 of gas in my truck just to drive to the gym, so many times I ran out of gas on the way home because I didn't have enough, but all I cared was going to the gym, I didn't care if I made it home...the gym was the most important part." For Jay, like many of the other bodybuilders, going to the gym was all that mattered to him. Similarly, Jason Coker discusses how he used to "drive from Indianapolis to here [Westside Barbell Gym] which is three hours," just so he could workout at Westside Barbell. These quotations demonstrate that for many of these men, bodybuilding becomes an obsession, they go to extreme lengths to work out and keep making themselves stronger.

Do whatever it takes

These men also have a mentality that you have to do whatever it takes, or that you can never do enough when it comes to building muscle. For example, Rich Piana says, “my suggestion is to have the mentality that you can never do too much, and also there is always someone out there doing more than you.” Rich is saying that you have to work extremely hard and keep adding more onto your training and eating routines in order to make progress. Louie Simmons holds a similar mentality, saying “you have to be able to do the mental training every day, got to do this freaking thing over and over, and it gets harder and harder.” Do whatever it takes is an extreme attitude held by many bodybuilders, and often it leads to their destructive behaviours. This is evident in the way they push their bodies to the extreme, often past healthy limits. This is clearly illustrated by Jason Coker, who says “You gotta be willing to endure pain...you know I broke my back three times, I fucking blew my fucking biceps off, ruptured discs, fucked my neck up, I can’t feel shit in this hand half the time, and I still do what I do, and I’m still going.” Jason is going to such extreme lengths that bodybuilding has become detrimental to his body, yet he continues to work out. Rich Piana also shares this attitude that training and eating are crucial and you cannot stop just because your body is uncomfortable. In order to get big Piana says, “it doesn’t matter if you’re not hungry, it doesn’t matter if you don’t have an appetite, you eat the fucking food.” This once again shows the extreme lengths that these men will push their bodies to as a result of being a bodybuilder.

Theme 4: High prevalence of steroids

Many of the bodybuilders in the YouTube videos acknowledge the high prevalence of steroids in the bodybuilding industry. The men either use them personally, know people who do, or just bring up their use in the video because they know how common steroids are in the industry. Pete Hartwig explains how “if anyone thinks that you can get to 250 pounds plus completely ripped without taking any substances then you’re probably really naïve.” Pete is saying that many people in the bodybuilding industry use steroids to get big and if you have not seen it, it does not mean that it is not happening, it just means that you are not aware. While drug use is not recommended or supported, most bodybuilders in the videos show indifference when it comes to taking steroids. For example, the confessions of a natural bodybuilder video explains Pete’s position when it comes to steroids: “We’ve all got our different paths and as long as we’re not in a position where we’re harming other people or putting pressure on other people to do things they don’t want to do, I think it’s a good thing.” A similar sentiment is expressed by Jason Coker in the Westside Barbell video: “As far as the substances go if you want to take drugs, take drugs, if you don’t want to take drugs, don’t take drugs. I respect all forms, raw, drug free, use drugs do whatever the fuck you want, snort cocaine on the platform I don’t give a fuck, but I don’t compete in drug free federations.” Jason expresses the stance that as long as you are not harming other people (using steroids in a drug-free competition), taking steroids is not a problem. Both Pete and Jason’s statements express a general acceptance of using steroids for bodybuilding purposes. Jason is also expressing the fact that he personally takes steroids to enhance his bodybuilding performance and would not compete any other way. Furthermore, Louie Simmons explains in the Westside Barbell video: “It’s not against the rules to take drugs, it’s against the rules to get caught taking drugs.” What Louie means is that steroids are so common that people essentially just accept that they are being used, you just cannot take them on the day of a competition. Overall, the videos share a similar view on steroids; they are common in the bodybuilding industry and as long as you are not hurting other people it is completely acceptable to take them in order to get bigger.

Theme 5: Body dissatisfaction

Many of the bodybuilders in the videos demonstrate persistent body dissatisfaction despite bodybuilding for some time. This dissatisfaction may be a lingering feeling from past insecurity or could be due to scrutiny they receive as professionals. This theme is clearly illustrated by Pete Hartwig when he says that “for a long time I’ve been completely obsessed with my physique and incredibly insecure about myself.” Furthermore, he discusses how prior to bodybuilding he thought that if he had an amazing body, he would not be insecure and unhappy anymore. However, Pete says, “I achieved my dream physique and it didn’t make me feel any happier, I actually felt worse.” Nick also shares similar feelings of insecurity even though he worked hard to achieve his body goals. Nick discusses how he “bulked up to 220” and he thought that if he cut down a bit “that I would get down

to where I'm shredded, I thought that was 190." However, when he started to lean down, in an attempt to become more muscular, he kept losing fat but was never satisfied with his body. Specifically, he says "I cut down to 190 from 220, still fat, so I'm sitting there at 190 thinking man if I can only get down to 175-180, I would be shredded to death, so I get down to 180 eh I'm not really fat but I'm still like I don't have a ripped six-pack." Nick continued to cut until he was 143 pounds, however even then he was not satisfied with his body, saying "I'm ashamed of how fucking small I was, I mean 143, that's what girls weigh." Both Nick and Pete demonstrate that bodybuilding for them did not improve their body dissatisfaction, and in fact may have exacerbated it further.

DISCUSSION

The purpose of this study was to investigate insights and perceptions about bodybuilding from competitors. YouTube videos were chosen as the data source, and themes were generated which were explored using thematic analysis. In total, five themes were generated: Influenced by social factors, Bodybuilding as a coping mechanism, Taking it to the extreme, High prevalence of steroids, and Body dissatisfaction. Taking it to the extreme was divided into two subthemes: Obsession and Do whatever it takes.

The notion that varying social factors can influence one to start bodybuilding is a well-known phenomenon in the literature. A study by Pope et al. (1999) found that certain popular American action toys (e.g., GI Joe, Luke Skywalker) have become progressively more muscular in the past 30 years. This likely reflects evolving ideals of the male body image, which could serve as a potential influence for someone to start bodybuilding. This is similar to how Theme 1 described comic book characters as major influencers for some of the bodybuilders to start their careers. Research tends to support that during early adolescence, boys may face pressure to meet the traditional Western male gender role; i.e., big, strong, and muscular (Galambos et al., 1990). These different exposures and social pressures can lead young boys to want to build muscles. Parents may also impact the decision to start bodybuilding, an idea that was substantiated by Ricciardelli et al. (2000). Although not explicitly stated in the YouTube videos, social media has also been found to motivate individuals to start working out or bodybuilding. A study on social media, specifically Instagram, showed that upward comparisons of the self to social media models motivated men to start working out (Peng et al., 2019).

A commonality surrounding many of the discussed social influences is that they represent a physique that is not attainable for the vast majority of people. While comic book characters and superheroes are often fictional characters, social media may depict similar physiques among "real" people. Social media is especially damaging to one's body image or self-esteem as one may be more likely to perceive that this physique is attainable when viewed on a real person versus a fictional character. However, there is a paucity of research that specifically compared the degree of influence held by fictional media versus social media, which represents an avenue for further exploration.

People on social media often post only the best photos of themselves, enhanced, or edited images (Fardouly & Vartanian, 2016). Additionally, there have been social media influencers who falsely claim to have natural bodies, when in reality they use performance enhancing drugs (PEDs) (Gibbs & Piatkowski, 2023). A prominent example of this in recent media was the influencer Brian Johnson, otherwise known as Liver King. Brian Johnson likely represents a larger issue present in social media of influencers claiming to be natural when they in fact use PEDs. The non-disclosure of PED use is problematic as it provides the observer with the illusion that a particular body physique is attainable despite this not being the case without the use of PEDs. This is significant because exposure to idealized body imagery has a negative effect on one's mood or body satisfaction (Fasoli & Constantinou, 2024).

The issue of non-disclosure of PEDs also came up in Theme 4 (Prevalence of steroids). It is well known that bodybuilding has a high prevalence of PED use among participants, despite varying region to region. A study by Al-Falasi and colleagues (2008) randomly sampled bodybuilders from 18 gyms in the United Arab Emirates and found that 22% had used anabolic steroids. Similarly, Alsaed

and Alabkal (2015) found that 23% of their random sample of bodybuilders in Kuwait had used anabolic steroids. Studies done on Western samples also seem to indicate a higher prevalence of steroid use among bodybuilders (Baker et al., 2006). Many of the bodybuilders portrayed in the YouTube videos believed that PED use was not an issue unless someone was claiming not to use them when they did in reality. Viewing a muscular person with the knowledge that they used PEDs to achieve their physique may be less damaging to the observer's body image or self-esteem, as opposed to being unaware of this fact. This is a relatively novel concept and represents an opportunity for further research. Despite the bodybuilders in the videos believing that non-disclosure of PED use was the main issue, it is important to keep in mind that this is not reality. There are numerous physical harms associated with using steroids such as higher risk of heart attack, liver cancer, and death (Daly et al., 2003). There are also psychological harms that can result from steroid use such as aggressive behaviour, irritability, and hypomania (Daly et al., 2003).

Theme 2 supports the idea that exercise can be used as a coping mechanism, which supports positive psychological well-being (Penedo & Dahn, 2005). The YouTube videos discussed how bodybuilding was used to improve or make the best of a negative situation. However, exercise, including bodybuilding, can go beyond healthy coping and become something more sinister. A study by Smith, et al., (1998) found that weight training is often initiated for reasons such as improving strength and fitness, but over time may take on an exaggerated importance. Similarly, there is a concept called exercise addiction, which refers to compulsive engagement in any form of physical exercise. Exercise addiction is characterised as having a craving for physical activity, and feelings of being incapable of living without it (Hausenblas & Downs, 2002). Physical activity becomes central to the person's life and dominates their thinking. Even if the person is not engaged in the behaviour, they will be thinking about the next time that they will be (Landolfi, 2013).

This concept of exercise addiction is closely tied to our subtheme Do whatever it takes. This theme also introduces the idea of pushing the body past its physical limits. There has been research that demonstrates that this is a commonality among many bodybuilders. For example, a qualitative study by Smith and Stewart (2012) used thematic analysis to analyse data that was obtained from a bodybuilding discussion forum. The researchers found that among the bodybuilders, there was a common idea that physical limits should be pushed, despite the potential physical pain or mental strain that could ensue. Similarly, Deighton-Smith and Bell (2018) conducted a qualitative study on the nature of images and text contained within social media posts using the #fitspiration hashtag. These individuals were more likely to overlook or fail to recognise bodily cues or sensitivity to pain, which may potentially affect future exercise performance or contribute to potential injury (Relejo, 2015).

In addition to enduring pain and injury, bodybuilders often adopt the mindset that they must eat extreme quantities of food in order to gain muscle, which was also discussed in the Do whatever it takes subtheme. On the opposite end of the spectrum, some bodybuilders also heavily restrict their caloric intake, especially before competitions. Both of these dieting patterns can lead to disordered eating among bodybuilders, such as bulimia nervosa and binge eating disorder, as found in a study by Goldfield et al. (2006). Specifically, this study found that almost 30% of competitive bodybuilders in a Canadian sample met the diagnostic criteria for bulimia nervosa at some point in their lives (Goldfield et al., 2006). The study also found that binge eating disorder was higher among competitive bodybuilders than recreational bodybuilders (Goldfield et al., 2006).

In addition to eating disorders, there is a disorder that is more specific to bodybuilders, called muscle dysmorphia (MD), also known as bigorexia. With MD, the affected individual believes that their body is too small or insufficiently muscular, even though in most cases, the individual is already exceptionally muscular (Leone et al., 2005). Individuals with MD demonstrate extreme insecurity about their bodies and are distressed at the thought of having one's body viewed by others (Pope et al., 1997). This belief of one's body being too small when it is in fact muscular, and the insecurity about one's body is extremely similar to sentiments expressed in the Body dissatisfaction theme. In addition, people with MD are never satisfied with their bodies, and will spend countless hours

engaging in activities in order to increase musculature (e.g., dieting, exercising, taking supplements). This concept ties back to previous themes as well, specifically Taking it to the extreme.

Overall narrative

Further analysis of our five themes resulted in a narrative that explains what happens before someone starts bodybuilding that may influence them to start, and what happens after they have been bodybuilding for some time. The men were mainly influenced by images of male body ideals portrayed in the media. Many of these are unrealistic ideals that are humanly impossible to attain (Pope et al., 1999). It is likely that idolizing these images of superhero physiques makes these men feel as if their bodies are not muscular enough, leading to insecurities and other psychological and behavioural problems. They then seek a way to alleviate these negative feelings and turn to bodybuilding as a coping mechanism. Although they may have good intentions when they begin training and eating like a bodybuilder, they often end up taking things to the extreme. They push themselves mentally and physically, however many of them are still not satisfied with how they look. Some bodybuilders then turn to steroids to boost their physical capabilities and help them achieve these standards they grew up looking up to. Many of the men do not view steroids as harmful; they know steroids will make them bigger and that is all that matters to them. However, in reality steroids can be extremely harmful. For example, Rich Piana died at the age of 46 due to an enlarged heart (von Wildenratt, 2017), which likely can be attributed to steroid use (Pärssinen & Seppälä, 2002). Others who choose not to take steroids may still have these feelings of insecurity, or never being satisfied with their body. This is evident in the fact that it was Nick and Pete, the only natural bodybuilders, who expressed feelings similar to those characteristic of muscle dysmorphia after bodybuilding.

LIMITATIONS

There were some limitations present in the study. The main limitation was the small sample size of five YouTube Videos. There are millions of videos on YouTube, and it is not possible to assess them all. Even within the subject of bodybuilding, there were many video formats that were excluded for the sake of a more focused research topic. This limits the ability to generalize the results to a larger bodybuilding community. Similarly, the data was collected from a single social media platform, which fails to account for potential alternative findings from other platforms. Furthermore, when using social media platforms as a data source, one is limited to what people feel comfortable posting online. More sensitive or personal information may be held back by the content creators. This type of data may be better suited to collection in a one-on-one interview style with individual bodybuilders, which could be a direction for further research. Finally, many of the research articles that were used to support the themes were written in the 1980s-1990s, which may represent a different consensus than what more current literature says about bodybuilding. This makes it possible that the themes that found could potentially not be supported with newer research.

Throughout the paper, several avenues for future research came up. One such avenue is whether viewing social media has more of an impact on body image and self-esteem when compared to fictional media. Additionally, it was suggested that viewing content from influencers or bodybuilders who admit to using PEDs to attain their physique may be less damaging to the body image or self-esteem of the viewer because they are aware that what they are seeing is not achievable naturally. This is in comparison to viewing content from people who falsely claim to be PED-free when this is not the case. This latter scenario may leave the viewer feeling more inadequate because they are led to believe that the body they are seeing is attainable without PED use. There was a sparsity of research to substantiate this hypothesis, and more exploration is needed to confirm what the authors propose. Finally, this study focused on a sample of competitive bodybuilders, and it is possible that they view and feel differently about bodybuilding than people who partake in the sport recreationally. One study by Goldfield and colleagues (2006) did compare differences between recreational and competitive bodybuilders in terms of eating disorders. However, there is still more to be learned about the differences among these populations in terms of other variables such as muscle dysmorphia or steroid use.

CONCLUSION

Our thematic analysis sought to identify insights and perceptions about bodybuilding as described by competitive bodybuilders. This study analysed five YouTube videos, a concept novel in this particular field of study. Findings indicate that bodybuilding can be used as a coping mechanism, which may help individuals in unfavourable situations. On the other hand, bodybuilding can have negative consequences such as disordered eating, muscle dysmorphia, body dissatisfaction, and steroid use. Overall, this study highlights that bodybuilding can be the product of good intentions, however it can become negative, especially because of its health risks when taken to the extreme.

Acknowledgements: None declared

Conflict of interests: None declared

Funding: None declared

Ethical approval: Not applicable

REFERENCES

- Al-Falasi, O., Al-Dahmani, K., Al-Eisaei, K., Al-Ameri, S., Al-Maskari, F., Nagelkerke, N., & Schneider, J. (2009). Knowledge, attitude and practice of anabolic steroids use among gym users in Al-Ain district, United Arab Emirates. *The Open Sports Medicine Journal*, 2(1), 75–81. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1874387000802010075>
- Alsaeed, I., & Alabkal, J. R. (2015). Usage and perceptions of anabolic-androgenic steroids among male fitness centre attendees in Kuwait – a cross-sectional study. *Substance Abuse Treatment Prevention and Policy*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13011-015-0030-5>
- ATLAS.ti. (2024, October 23). *Deductive thematic analysis: Definition & method*. Retrieved from <https://atlasti.com/guides/thematic-analysis/deductive-thematic-analysis>
- Baker, J.S., Graham, M.R., & Davies, B. (2006). Steroid and prescription medicine abuse in the health and fitness community: A regional study. *European Journal of Internal Medicine*, 17(7), 479–484. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejim.2006.04.010>
- Barlett, C., Harris, R., Smith, S., & Bonds-Raacke, J. (2005). Action figures and men. *Sex Roles*, 53(11–12), 877–885. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11199-005-8304-4>
- Barlett, C. P., Vowels, C. L., & Saucier, D. A. (2008). Meta-Analyses of the effects of media images on men's body-image concerns. *Journal of Social and Clinical Psychology*, 27(3), 279–310. <https://doi.org/10.1521/jscp.2008.27.3.279>
- Blouin, A. G., & Goldfield, G. S. (1995). Body image and steroid use in male bodybuilders. *International Journal of Eating Disorders*, 18(2), 159–165. [https://doi.org/10.1002/1098-108X\(199509\)18:2<159::AID-EAT2260180208>3.0.CO;2-3](https://doi.org/10.1002/1098-108X(199509)18:2<159::AID-EAT2260180208>3.0.CO;2-3)
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77–101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp0630a>
- Cash, T. F. (1990). The psychology of physical appearance: Aesthetics, attributes, and images. In T. F. Cash & T. Pruzinsky (Eds.), *Body images: Development, deviance, and change* (pp. 51–79). Guilford Press.
- Cash, T. F. (2004). Body image: Past, present, and future. *Body Image*, 1(1), 1–5. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1740-1445\(03\)00011-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1740-1445(03)00011-1)
- Daly, R., Su, T., Schmidt, P., Pagliaro, M., Pickar, D., & Rubinow, D. R.. (2003). Neuroendocrine and behavioral effects of high-dose anabolic steroid administration in male normal volunteers. *Psychoneuroendocrinology*, 28(3), 317–331. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0306-4530\(02\)00025-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0306-4530(02)00025-2)
- Deighton-Smith, N., & Bell, B. T. (2018). Objectifying fitness: A content and thematic analysis of #fitspiration images on social media. *Psychology of Popular Media Culture*, 7(4), 467. <https://doi.org/10.1037/ppm0000143>
- Dimeo, F., Bauer, M., Varahram, I., Proest, G., & Halter, U. (2001). Benefits from aerobic exercise in patients with major depression: a pilot study. *British journal of sports medicine*, 35, 114–117. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/bjism.35.2.114>
- Fardouly, J., & Vartanian, L. R. (2016). Social media and body image concerns: Current research and future directions. *Current Opinion in Psychology*, 9, 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.copsyc.2015.09.005>
- Fasoli, F., & Constantinou, D. (2024). Does body positivity work for men as it does for women? The impact of idealized body and body positive imagery on body satisfaction, drive for thinness, and drive for muscularity. *Acta Psychologica*, 243, 104126. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actpsy.2024.104126>
- Galambos, N. L., Almeida, D. M., & Petersen, A. C. (1990). Masculinity, Femininity, and Sex Role Attitudes in Early Adolescence: Exploring Gender Intensification. *Child Development*, 61(6), 1905. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1130846>
- Generation Iron Fitness & Bodybuilding Network. (2017, May 15) Jay Cutler interview: I didn't want to be big, I wanted to win | Iron Cinema [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=orCvEiij-OA>
- Gibbs, N., & Piatkowski, T. (2023). The Liver King Lie: Misrepresentation, justification, and public health implications. *International Journal of Drug Policy*, 114, 103979. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.drugpo.2023.103979>

- Goldfield, G. S., Blouin, A. G., & Woodside, D. B. (2006). Body image, binge eating, and bulimia nervosa in male bodybuilders. *The Canadian Journal of Psychiatry*, 51(3), 160–168. <https://doi.org/10.1177/070674370605100306>
- Hausenblas, H. A., & Downs, D. S. (2002). Exercise dependence: a systematic review. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, 3(2), 89–123. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s1469-0292\(00\)00015-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/s1469-0292(00)00015-7)
- Henwood, K. L., & Pidgeon, N. F. (1992). Qualitative research and psychological theorizing. *British Journal of Psychology*, 83(1), 97–111. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2044-8295.1992.tb02426.x>
- Klein, A. M. (1986). Pumping Irony: Crisis and contradiction in bodybuilding. *Sociology of Sport Journal*, 3(2), 112–133. <https://doi.org/10.1123/ssj.3.2.112>
- Landolfi, E. (2013). Exercise addiction. *Sports Medicine*, 43(2), 111–119. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40279-012-0013-x>
- Leone, J. E., Sedory, E. J., & Gray, K. A. (2005). Recognition and treatment of muscle dysmorphia and related body image disorders. *Journal of athletic training*, 40(4), 352–359.
- Navigating YouTube Search - How YouTube Works. (n.d.). Navigating YouTube Search - How YouTube Works. <https://www.youtube.com/howyoutubeworks/product-features/search/>
- Nick's Strength and Power. (2017, February 6). The truth about natural bodybuilding. . . [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rBC1UEhy4So>
- O'Connor, P. J., Herring, M. P., & Caravalho, A. (2010). Mental health benefits of strength training in adults. *American Journal of Lifestyle Medicine*, 4(5), 377–396. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1559827610368771>
- Pärssinen, M., & Seppälä, T. (2002). Steroid use and Long-Term health risks in former athletes. *Sports Medicine*, 32(2), 83–94. <https://doi.org/10.2165/00007256-200232020-00001>
- Penedo, F. J., & Dahn, J. R. (2005). Exercise and well-being: a review of mental and physical health benefits associated with physical activity. *Current opinion in psychiatry*, 18(2), 189–193. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00001504-200503000-00013>
- Peng, C., Wu, T., Chen, Y., & Atkin, D. J. (2019). Comparing and modeling via social media: The social influences of fitspiration on male instagram users' work out intention. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 99, 156–167. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2019.05.011>
- Pete Hartwig. (2018, May 1). Confessions of a “natural” bodybuilder | Pete Hartwig | 2018 [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tNCxw11Wds>
- Pope, H. G., Gruber, A. J., Choi, P., Olivardia, R., & Phillips, K. A. (1997). Muscle dysmorphia: an underrecognized form of body dysmorphic disorder. *Psychosomatics*, 38(6), 548–557. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0033-3182\(97\)71400-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0033-3182(97)71400-2)
- Pope, H. G., Jr, Olivardia, R., Gruber, A., & Borowiecki, J. (1999). Evolving ideals of male body image as seen through action toys. *The International journal of eating disorders*, 26(1), 65–72. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(sici\)1098-108x\(199907\)26:1<65::aid-eat8>3.0.co;2-d](https://doi.org/10.1002/(sici)1098-108x(199907)26:1<65::aid-eat8>3.0.co;2-d)
- Relajo, D. (2015). A randomised controlled trial on brief expressive writing as an intervention tool on exposure to thin-ideal images. *Journal on Innovation in Psychology, Education and Didactics*, 19(2), 295–306. <http://doi.org/d649>
- Ricciardelli, L. A., McCabe, M. P., & Banfield, S. (2000). Body image and body change methods in adolescent boys. *Journal of Psychosomatic Research*, 49(3), 189–197. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0022-3999\(00\)00159-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0022-3999(00)00159-8)
- Rich Piana. (2015, February 10). The secret to getting big - Rich Piana | 2015 [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vs2IQNk10bw>
- Smith, A. C. T., & Stewart, B. (2012). Body perceptions and health behaviors in an online bodybuilding community. *Qualitative Health Research*, 22(7), 971–985. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1049732312443425>
- Smith, D. K., Hale, B. D., & Collins, D. (1998). Measurement of exercise dependence in bodybuilders. *The Journal of sports medicine and physical fitness*, 38(1), 66–74.
- Thelwall, M., Sud, P., & Vis, F. (2011). Commenting on YouTube videos: From guatemalan rock to El Big Bang. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 63(3), 616–629. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.21679>
- Tsutsumi, T., Don, B. M., Zaichkowsky, L. D., & Delizonna, L. L. (1997). Physical fitness and psychological benefits of strength training in community dwelling older adults. *APPLIED HUMAN SCIENCE Journal of Physiological Anthropology*, 16(6), 257–266. <https://doi.org/10.2114/jpa.16.257>

- VICE Sports. (2018, February 22). Inside Westside Barbell, powerlifting's most exclusive and controversial gym [Video]. YouTube. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=AvHM7H_hh8o
- von Wildenrad, R. (2017, November 9). Bodybuilder Rich Piana's autopsy finds "drug involvement could not be ruled out." *Men's Health*. <https://www.menshealth.com/trending-news/a19541843/bodybuilder-rich-piana-autopsy-report>
- Walsh, S. (2024, September 18). The top 10 social media sites & platforms. *Search Engine Journal*. <https://www.searchenginejournal.com/social-media/social-media-platforms>
- Yesalis, C. E., & Bahrke, M. S. (2002). Anabolic-Androgenic steroids and related substances. *Current Sports Medicine Reports*, 1(4), 246–252. <https://doi.org/10.1249/00149619-200208000-00009>
- YouTube. (n.d.). *Navigating YouTube search: How YouTube works*. Retrieved from <https://www.youtube.com/howyoutubeworks/product-features/search>